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Enhancing transcranial ultrasound stimulation planning with MRI-derived skull masks: a comparative analysis with CT-based processing

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Supplementary material for this article is available [online](#)

Abstract

Objective. Transcranial ultrasound stimulation (TUS) presents challenges in ultrasound wave transmission through the skull, affecting study outcomes due to aberration and attenuation. While planning strategies incorporating 3D computed tomography (CT) scans help mitigate these issues, they expose participants to radiation, which can raise ethical concerns. A solution involves generating skull masks from participants' anatomical magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). This study aims to compare ultrasound field predictions between CT-derived and MRI-derived skull masks in TUS planning. **Approach.** Five participants with a range of skull density ratios (SDRs: 0.31, 0.42, 0.55, 0.67, and 0.79) were selected, each having both CT and T1/T2-weighted MRI scans. Ultrasound simulations were performed using BabelBrain software with a single-element transducer (diameter = 50 mm, $F\# = 1$) at 250, 500, and 750 kHz frequencies. CT scans were used to generate maps of the skull's acoustic properties. The MRI scans were processed using the Charm segmentation tool from the SimNIBS tool suite using default and custom settings adapted for better skull segmentation. Ultrasound was adjusted to target 30 mm below the skull's surface at 54 electroencephalogram (EEG) locations. **Main Results.** The custom setting in Charm significantly improved the Dice coefficient between MRI- and CT-derived masks when compared to the default setting ($p < 0.001$). The maximum pressure error significantly decreased in the custom setting compared to the default setting ($p < 0.001$). Additionally, the focus location error median across different SDRs averaged 2.32, 1.45, and 1.57 mm in default and 2.08, 1.38, and 1.44 mm in custom conditions for 250 kHz, 500 kHz, and 750 kHz respectively. **Significance.** MRI-derived skull masks offer satisfactory accuracy at many EEG sites, and using custom settings can further enhance this accuracy. However, significant errors at specific locations highlight the importance of carefully considering stimulation location when choosing between CT- and MRI-derived skull modeling.

1. Introduction

Transcranial ultrasound stimulation (TUS) represents an innovative approach utilizing ultrasound energy to alter brain structure or function, with applications ranging from brain tissue ablation and activity modulation to the facilitation of therapeutic agent delivery through the blood–brain barrier [1–3].

One of the primary technical challenges in effectively deploying transcranial ultrasound therapies is the transmission of ultrasound waves through the intact skull. The skull can introduce substantial distortions and attenuation to the waves, which complicates achieving the intended therapeutic outcomes [4, 5]. To address these challenges, planning techniques are utilized to rectify the distortions caused by the skull, often employing a pre-acquired 3D computed tomography (CT) scan of the patient’s skull [6]. These corrections are vital for the precise targeting of ultrasound waves on specific brain regions.

The use of computer simulations plays a pivotal role in overcoming the barriers posed by the skull [7]. These simulations are primarily based on acoustic property maps derived from CT images, enabling the prediction of the intracranial pressure field and the adjustment of phase delays to achieve a coherent focus at the target site. CT is used to generate the required skull map because it provides high-resolution images with excellent bone contrast, which makes it easy to identify the complex heterogeneity of the skull [8, 9]. The Hounsfield values of CT are transformed into maps of acoustic properties such as density, speed of sound and attenuation [6, 10–14] that become the input of the numerical models [7].

The requirement for CT imaging in studies, especially those involving healthy participants, can raise ethical concerns due to the exposure to ionizing radiation. This situation underscores the benefits of an alternative TUS planning protocol that incorporates a safer, non-ionizing imaging alternative for skull mapping. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scans present a promising avenue in this regard. MR-only ultrasound planning simplifies the process by requiring only one scan and eliminating the need for inter-modality registration, reducing potential registration and targeting errors. Anatomical T1- and T2-weighted images can be processed to produce segmentation of head tissues. While multiple brain imaging processing suites such as Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging of the Brain (FMRIB) Software Library (FSL) [15], Analysis of Functional NeuroImages (AFNI) [16] and FreeSurfer [17] contain functions to segment the brain tissue and strip the scalp and skull bone, these tissues are often not preserved in the segmentation as an output. The tool SimNIBS [18] is a well-established and continuously updated software suite for processing head MRI scans to simulate non-invasive neuromodulation techniques such as transcranial

magnetic and electric stimulation. Segmenting and preserving segmentation of scalp and skull tissues is critical to this type of simulation. The SimNIBS v4.1’s Charm tool [19] automates whole-head segmentation directly from T1- and T2-weighted scans. Charm relies on a Bayesian segmentation approach, which combines a probabilistic prior with an intensity model to capture how different tissues appear on MRI scans. The intensity model is parameterized using a Gaussian Mixture Model where the user can choose how many Gaussians are used to model each tissue class. The tissue classes can also be freely chosen, so that structures that appear similar in the MRI scan are modeled together. For instance, in fat-suppressed MRI scans, spongy bone and compact bone can appear similar, so they can be modeled as a single tissue class.

Alternatively, recent studies are exploring utilizing machine learning methods to produce synthetic CT calculated from T1-weighted scans [20, 21], but those methods so far rely on very specific T1-weighted scanning conditions that may not be easily transferable between sites or for which training with paired CT scans is required per-site basis. Ultra short echo time (UTE) MR scans [22] such as zero echo time (ZTE), UTE or pointwise-encoding time reduction with radial acquisition (PETRA) are interesting candidates to produce synthetic CT scans [23] for TUS planning purposes, given these scans produce adequate contrast for the inner skull structure comparable to CT scans. Previous work has demonstrated that a simple series of linear transformations can adequately approximate synthetic CT scans from ZTE for TUS planning [23]. However, availability for this type of MR scan is not currently ensured across sites. One critical advantage of well-established tools such as Charm is the resilience of the underlying method [19] to variations in contrasts across MRI systems vendors, which makes it an attractive candidate for a universal tool for TUS planning.

For TUS planning purposes, skull information can be incorporated using a homogenous mask with average values of skull acoustic properties (density, speed of sound and attenuation) or mapping methods to convert from Hounsfield units (HUs) to these properties [24]. Several studies have evaluated the limitations of using a homogenous mask to represent the skull bone in the context of the prediction of transcranial ultrasound for therapy purposes. Leung *et al* compared the difference in peak pressure for ultrasound refocusing with an MRI-guided focused ultrasound (MRIGFUS) system for brain therapy (Exablate Neuro, Insightec, Haifa, Israel) when using a homogenous mask derived from CT thresholding, mappings using synthetic HU derived from UTE and real HU scan, and hydrophone based refocusing using three skull specimens [25]. Numerical refocusing used proprietary ray tracing methods from the vendor. Compared to hydrophone-based refocusing,

it was found that using a simple mask could recover $64 \pm 7\%$ of peak pressure at the intended target, while synthetic and real CT recovered $71 \pm 2\%$ and $71 \pm 15\%$, respectively. Drainville *et al* used the same MRigFUS system to compare the resulting peak pressure using homogenous masks derived from HU (no mapping), to layered models of skull bone in trabecular and cortical bone using a ray tracer model [26]. Authors found that using a homogenous mask could overestimate the transmitted peak pressure from 20% to 70% depending on the heterogeneity of the skull bone. For MRI-based masks of the skull bone, a previous study established the expected difference in ultrasound energy transmission when using MRI-only derived homogenous masks using the Charm tool and with HU-derived mapping [24]. For a single target representative of the motor cortex, using a commercially available TUS device (CTX-500, Sonicconcepts, USA) operating at 650 kHz, differences in peak pressure—compared to CT-based simulations—ranged from -14.7% to 24.4% , depending on the degree of skull heterogeneity [24]. Differences in the focal spot volume ranged from -5.0% to 40% . While these observations provided a preliminary evaluation of the to-be-expected degree of difference between TUS simulations based on tissue masks derived from T1- and T2-weighted MRI scans and CT-derived bone density estimates, it is critical to expand the scope of those findings to more head regions and ultrasound frequencies.

In this study, we aimed to delve into the accuracy of TUS by comparing ultrasound beam predictions between conventional CT-based approaches and MRI-based methods across multiple head locations based on EEG landmarks, aiming to establish the level of confidence per landmark basis for ultrasound stimulation planning based on conventional T1- and T2-weighted MR images. Additionally, we optimized the settings of the Charm tool to enhance transcranial ultrasound stimulation planning with MRI-derived skull masks. In this study, where the MRI scans are not fat-suppressed, spongy bone and subcutaneous fat were modeled together due to their similar intensities. These customizable settings in Charm allow for more flexible and accurate segmentation across different types of MRI data.

2. Methods

2.1. Dataset

Transcranial ultrasound simulations were conducted using MRI and CT scans from patients treated for essential tremor and obsessive-compulsive disorder with MRigFUS at the University of Calgary. The analysis in this manuscript is based on data from a previous study that was approved by the University

of Calgary Conjoint Health Research Ethics Board (REB22-0235). The study adhered to the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. Five participants representing a range of skull density ratios (SDRs) ranging from 0.31 to 0.79 were used in the study using a publicly accessible repository (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7894431](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7894431)). The SDR is a metric that measures the ratio of the HUs of the trabecular region of the skull bone over the cortical region. Lower values of SDR are associated with higher attenuation of ultrasound transmission. In this study, SDR values were calculated by the Exablate Neuro console (Insightec, Haifa, Israel) using CT scans by measuring the HU ratio along the trajectories between the active elements of the transducer array and the target, which was the left ventral intermediate nucleus of the thalamus. The SDR values calculated by the planning software of the MRgFUS Neuro system (Exablate, Haifa, Israel), which were examined in this study, were 0.31, 0.42, 0.55, 0.67, and 0.79.

2.2. Image acquisition

CT imaging was conducted using a Discovery CT750 HD scanner (GE, MW, USA) at an energy level of 120 kVp. This process utilized the BONEPLUS reconstruction kernel, achieving a pixel resolution of 0.45 mm, with a slice thickness of 0.625 mm and an interslice spacing of 0.66 mm. The skull bone region underwent thresholding in the range of 300–2100 HUs.

Concurrently, T1- and T2-weighted scans with 1 mm isotropic resolution were obtained with a Discovery 750 3 T MRI scanner (GE, MW, USA). T1w scans employed BRAVO, GE's proprietary 3D inversion recovery-prepared fast spoiled gradient echo sequence, with parameters set to TR = 8.2 ms, TE = 3.2 ms, TI = 650 ms, a flip angle of 10° , a field of view of $256 \times 256 \times 188$ mm, and an acquisition matrix of $256 \times 256 \times 188$.

For T2w scans, a 3D fast spin-echo technique was used, featuring parameters of TR = 3000 ms, TE = 60–90 ms, an echo train length of 130, a field of view of $256 \times 225 \times 188$ mm, and an acquisition matrix of $256 \times 256 \times 188$ (which was zero-filled to $512 \times 512 \times 376$).

2.3. Pre-processing and skull mask extraction

T1- and T2-weighted scans were processed using the Charm tool in the SimNIBS 4.1 software package [19] with both the default and a custom setup. In the custom setup, we used an updated tissue atlas where the extra-cerebral soft tissues are split into fat and the remaining structures correspond roughly to muscle tissue. To model the intensity of the fat tissue in the non-fat-suppressed MRI scans, we assigned a separate Gaussian distribution to the fat class as well as the spongy bone class, which contains fat and appears

bright in the T1-weighted scan.⁹ This differs from the standard Charm segmentation settings, where the fat is a part of the so-called scalp class, and the intensities of the spongy and compact bone tissues are modeled jointly. Details of the intensity model and the segmentation algorithm can be found in [19]. From the outputs of the Charm tool, the masks for spongy and compact bone were combined in a single mask of the skull region. The electroencephalogram (EEG) locations in the scalp region were automatically identified as part of the automatic segmentation performed by Charm.

2.4. Transcranial ultrasound modeling

The ultrasound simulation was performed using the BabelBrain v0.3.5 [24] software employing a simple focusing single-element transducer at 250, 500 and 750 kHz. For modeling purposes, trajectories were generated for each EEG location, ensuring normal incidence (90°) to the scalp's surface. However, specific locations (Fp1, Fp2, Fpz, LPA, Nz, P9, P10, RPA, Afz, AF8, AF7, AF4, AF3) were omitted due to complications such as passage through air-filled structures, proximity to the ear, or issues with mask generation attributed to defacing of the MRI scans. Defacing algorithms, designed to retain brain tissue, can sometimes be overly aggressive due to variability in facial features. This often impacts areas like Afz, AF8, AF7, AF4, and AF3, where facial features and brain regions intersect, leading to the inadvertent removal of anatomical landmarks. Additionally, the Iz location for SDR of 0.31 was excluded since the target in the 30 mm distance ended up in the skull, not the brain. Consequently, 54 EEG locations were suitable for analysis. The O1 and O2 trajectories for SDR of 0.67 were manually adjusted due to locally poor skin segmentation using Charm. The target for focusing ultrasound was adjusted to penetrate 30 mm deep from the scalp surface for all considered EEG locations. Figure 1 shows a schematic of the simulation setup and selected EEG locations.

For MRI-based simulations, label masks representing skin, skull, and brain were generated with a resolution of six points-per-wavelength (PPW) for frequencies of 500 kHz and 750 kHz in water conditions. For simulations at 250 kHz, the resolution was increased to nine PPW to represent thin bone structures, such as the parietal bone, more accurately. Preliminary work demonstrated that 6 PPW is largely sufficient to ensure accurate modeling of focusing ultrasound using the Rayleigh–Sommerfeld integral as the gold standard. Metrics shown in table S1 and figure S7 in the appendix indicate that differences in maximum pressure, volume at -6 dB and distance of maximum pressure were, respectively, less than

⁹ https://github.com/ProteusMRIgHIFU/EnhanceTUS_Zadeh_JNE.

Figure 1. (A) Electroencephalogram (EEG) locations selected for simulations, with certain sites (Fp1, Fp2, Fpz, LPA, Nz, P9, P10, RPA, Afz, AF8, AF7, AF4, AF3) excluded due to factors such as passage through air-filled structures, proximity to the ear, or challenges in mask generation resulting from magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scan defacing. (B) Schematic of the simulation setup, where the ultrasound focus was consistently adjusted to target a depth of 30 mm beneath the scalp surface across all included EEG locations using a single-element transducer with the diameter of 50 mm.

0.49%, 1.3% and 0.7 mm. The skull was modeled as consisting of three layers—cortical (10%), trabecular (80%), and cortical (10%) as suggested in a previous study of intercomparison between different numerical models for transcranial ultrasound [27]. MRI images were used to obtain the thickness map of the skull rather than provide detailed voxel-level information, as the porous trabecular bone is difficult to detect with standard T1- and T2-weighted images. For the MRI-based simulations, the material properties are listed in table 1.

For the CT-based simulations, the label masks were refined to include voxel-level information about the skull bone at the same PPW resolution as those used in the MRI-based simulations. Adjustments were made to the T1w scans to correct for bias and align their resolution with that of CT scans, followed by co-registration to the T1w space. A user-defined threshold (default to 300 HU) was applied,

Table 1. Material properties for homogenized materials. ρ : density. c_L : longitudinal speed. c_S : shear speed. α_L : longitudinal attenuation. α_S : shear attenuation. f : frequency (MHz) [24].

Tissue	ρ (Kg m ⁻³)	c_L (m s ⁻¹)	c_S (m s ⁻¹)	α_L (Np m ⁻¹ MHz ⁻¹)	α_S (Np m ⁻¹ MHz ⁻¹)
Water	1000	1500	—	—	—
Skin	1116	1537	—	4.6 f^1	—
Brain	1041	1562	—	6.9 f^1	—
Cortical bone	1896.5	2415 120 f	1369 346 f	163 f^1	329 f^1
Trabecular bone	1738	2063 282 f	1206 212 f	162 f^1	329 f^1

and CT values in the thresholded region were quantified with 12 bits of resolution. Then, the mapping from HU to density, speed of sound, and attenuation was performed using the ‘Webb-Marsac’ approach, as detailed in previous work [24]. The fitting parameters were selected for a GE scanner operating at 120 kVp, using a BONEPLUS kernel reconstruction, with axial and slice resolutions of 0.5 mm and 0.6 mm, respectively.

2.5. Error metrics

This study compared several outcomes for each EEG location and participant across MRI- and CT-based simulations, including alignment of the skull masks as measured by the Dice coefficient, error in maximum pressure within the brain, error in the focus volume size (calculated at -6 dB), and error in the focus location. For the Dice coefficient calculations, a CT-derived binary mask was calculated with the threshold region mentioned above, and the MRI-derived mask comprised all regions identified as trabecular and cortical bone. Dice coefficients were reported across different frequencies, each with different spatial resolutions, to account for any potential effects of the smoothing filters applied during the voxelization of the isosurfaces on the resulting 3D masks. These comparisons were conducted to ascertain the precision and reliability of both simulation methodologies. The focus location error was calculated using the following formula:

$$FLE = \sqrt{(x_{MR} - x_{CT})^2 + (y_{MR} - y_{CT})^2 + (z_{MR} - z_{CT})^2} \quad (1)$$

where FLE represents the focus location error, x and y represent the coordinates of the focal point aligned with the transducer’s axis, and z denotes the coordinate of the focal point along the direction of wave propagation. MR represents the MRI-derived condition and CT represents the CT-derived condition.

The simulation domain had dimensions of $54 \times 54 \times 104$ mm, which covered the incident acoustic beam path plus 40 mm beyond the target. A Jupyter Python notebook was developed to

execute the steps involved in BabelBrain software in batch mode. Focus location and volume were calculated with the `regionprops_table` function of the `scikit-image` library. Examples of batch mode processing are available at BabelBrain’s GitHub repository (<https://github.com/ProteusMRIgHIFU/BabelBrain>). The source code for this study is available in a public repository (see data availability statement).⁹

2.6. Statistical analysis

Since the data was not normally distributed, the Wilcoxon rank-sum test (Mann–Whitney U test) was used to assess overall differences between the custom and default settings for the error metrics. P -values and common language effect sizes (CL) were calculated for each metric to determine the statistical significance. To account for multiple comparisons and reduce the risk of type I errors, the Bonferroni correction was applied to the p -values in the post hoc analysis. The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$.

3. Results

3.1. Dice coefficient

Figure 2(A) illustrates the Dice coefficients comparing MRI- and CT-derived binary masks under both default and custom settings. The median Dice coefficients ranged from 0.76 to 0.86 across all SDRs and frequencies in the default setting. However, in the custom setting, the Dice coefficients significantly increased, ranging from 0.83 to 0.92, indicating improvement in the skull mask generation ($CL = 0.7$, $p < 0.001$). Generally, MRI-based skull masks underestimated the skull thickness when compared to CT. Also worth mentioning is that certain locations exhibited Dice coefficients below 0.5 in the default setting. Specifically, this occurred at location F7 for the SDR of 0.31 at all fundamental frequencies (FFs); at location F5 for the SDR of 0.31 at FFs of 500 kHz and 750 kHz; at location C1 for the SDR of 0.67 at all FFs; and at location C2 for the SDR of 0.67 at FFs of 250 kHz and 500 kHz. Figure 2(B) illustrates an instance where the MRI-derived masks showed sub-optimal accuracy in the default setting, underestimating skull thickness by 36% in the center of the mask. However, this underestimation of the thickness was only 7% in the custom setting.

Figure 2. (A) Dice coefficients comparing MRI- and CT-derived masks across the three frequencies (250, 500 and 750 kHz) under both default and custom settings. Each violin displays the distribution of data; dots within each violin represent each EEG location; horizontal lines represent the median value. (B) Example illustrating the coronal view of a case where MRI-derived masks demonstrated suboptimal accuracy under the default setting but showed improved accuracy when using the custom setting.

3.2 Maximum pressure and volume size

When comparing the average maximum pressure across the five SDRs, the differences between simulations based on MRI- and CT-derived masks are minimal in both settings for the frequency of 500 kHz (figure 3(A)). For detailed plots at frequencies of 250 kHz and 750 kHz, please refer to figures S1 and S3 in the appendix. A closer examination of the maximum pressure for each SDR (figure 3(B)—see appendix for frequencies of 250 and 750 kHz) reveals a distinct pattern. Compared to CT-based predictions, it was found that in the MRI-derived masks, the maximum pressure was overestimated for SDRs of 0.31 and 0.42, while it was underestimated for SDRs of 0.55, 0.67, and 0.79.

For 250 kHz, the mean (SD) difference between maximum pressure for MRI-based and CT-based simulations was 0.015 (0.037) MPa in the default setting, and 0.007 (0.032) MPa in the custom setting.

At 500 kHz, the mean (SD) difference between maximum pressure for MRI-based and CT-based simulations was 0.01 (0.052) MPa in the default setting, and -0.002 (0.051) MPa in the custom setting.

For 750 kHz, the mean (SD) difference between maximum pressure for MRI-based and CT-based simulations was -0.021 (0.085) MPa in the default

setting, and -0.037 (0.08) MPa in the custom setting. Additionally, the differences in maximum pressure between higher and lower SDRs are more pronounced at higher frequencies compared to lower frequencies.

The differences in CT-based simulations between default and custom conditions arise from the soft tissue segmentation obtained from the output of Charm, which may vary across these conditions. These variations can impact the estimated tissue thickness and target trajectory, ultimately influencing the outcomes of the CT-based simulations.

Figure 3(D) illustrates the volume size distribution for each SDR at a frequency of 500 kHz. For detailed results at frequencies of 250 kHz and 750 kHz, please refer to figures S1 and S3 in the appendix.

For 250 kHz, the mean (SD) difference between maximum pressure for MRI-based and CT-based simulations was 156.6 (613.5) mm³ in the default setting, and 118.2 (720) mm³ in the custom setting.

For 500 kHz, the mean (SD) difference between maximum pressure for MRI-based and CT-based simulations was -45.5 (135) mm³ in the default setting, and -42.3 (135) mm³ in the custom setting.

For 750 kHz, the mean (SD) difference between maximum pressure for MRI-based and CT-based

Figure 3. (A) The average of the maximum pressure in MPa for the 5 skull density ratios (SDRs) at each electroencephalogram (EEG) location in both default and custom settings simulations compared to computed tomography (CT) simulations. (B) Violin plot showing the distribution of maximum pressure for each SDR in both default and custom settings simulations compared to CT simulations. Dots within each violin represent each EEG location; horizontal lines represent the median value. (C) The average volume size for the 5 SDRs at each EEG location in both default and custom settings simulations compared to CT simulations. (D) Violin plot showing the distribution of volume size for each SDR in both default and custom settings simulations compared to CT simulations. Dots within each violin represent each EEG location; horizontal lines represent the median value. All simulations were conducted at the 500 kHz frequency.

simulations was -25.3 (79.5) mm^3 in the default setting, and -26.3 (91.8) mm^3 in the custom setting.

Overall, CT-based simulations exhibited slightly larger volumes at the analyzed locations, but no major variations in volume size were observed with respect to SDR values for either MRI or CT-based simulations.

3.3. Error metrics between MRI- and CT-based simulations

In analyzing the error associated with the maximum pressure between MRI- and CT-based simulations, we observed the following median error ranges across the five SDRs at different frequencies: In the default setting, the error ranged from -7.22% to 25.64% at 250 kHz, from -12.33% to 29.54% at 500 kHz, and from -27.81% to 44.34% at 750 kHz. In the custom setting, the error ranged from -12.86% to 14.5% at 250 kHz, from -9.75% to 18.16% at 500 kHz, and from -33.1% to 19.14% at 750 kHz (table 1). Statistical analysis revealed a significant decrease in maximum pressure error in the custom setting compared to the default setting ($CL = 0.437$, $p < 0.001$). Post hoc analysis indicated that the pressure error at 250 kHz and 500 kHz was significantly lower in the custom setting compared to the default setting ($CL = 0.435$, $p = 0.034$ and $CL = 0.427$, $p = 0.013$, respectively). Although the error also decreased for the 750 kHz frequency, it did not reach statistical significance ($CL = 0.441$, $p = 0.068$). Figures 4(A) and 5(A) illustrate the mean and standard deviation of the maximum pressure error for each EEG location at a frequency of 500 kHz, under default and custom settings respectively. For details on the other frequencies, refer to figures S2, S3, S5 and S6.

Regarding the volume size error between MRI- and CT-based simulations, statistical analysis did not reveal any significant difference between the default and custom settings ($CL = 0.508$, $p = 0.489$). Figures 4(B) and 5(B) show the mean and standard deviation of the volume size error for each EEG location at the frequency of 500 kHz, under default and custom settings respectively.

For the error in focus location between MRI- and CT-based simulations, statistical analysis did not reveal any significant difference between the default and custom settings ($CL = 0.484$, $p = 0.335$). The mean and standard deviation changes for each EEG location at the frequency of 500 kHz, under default and custom settings are presented in figures 4(C) and 5(C), respectively.

Lastly, figures 4(D) and 5(D) display a color map representing the standard deviation of the error for each EEG location concerning maximum pressure, volume size, and focus location, for the frequency of 500 kHz, providing a visual summary of the variability observed in default and custom settings respectively.

Furthermore, table 2 presents the median of the error (95% confidence intervals) for each SDR and each analyzed variable. This detailed overview offers a perspective on the variability and reliability of the differences between MRI- and CT-based simulations across different measures and frequencies.

3.4. Computational cost

Simulations were performed on a MacBook Pro (M3 Max, 128 GB memory). For MRI-based conditions, computing wall-times of a single simulation for 250, 500, and 750 kHz were 44.9, 83.1, and 289 s, respectively, and for CT-based conditions, they were 112.9, 177, and 484.6 s, in the same order. A total of 2430 simulations were conducted, spanning 54 EEG locations, 5 datasets, 3 frequencies, and 3 input settings. The accumulated computing time was 5.02 d, with the BabelBrain solver consuming 20%. Simulations at 750 kHz required up to 78 GB of memory, with prior tests showing feasibility on 64 GB systems.

4. Discussion

Transcranial ultrasound stimulation represents a novel approach for a variety of scientific and therapeutic applications, emphasizing the necessity of simulations for optimizing treatment efficacy and ensuring safety. These simulations are complicated because of the need for precision in modeling the skull structure.

In this study, we explored two distinct methodologies for planning transcranial ultrasound stimulations, focusing on comparing ultrasound predictions when the skull region is modeled with homogeneous masks derived from MRI versus CT-derived maps of acoustic properties. Although using the custom settings in MRI-based simulations significantly decreased the maximum pressure error, further improvement in the MRI data processing to produce skull regions that are closer in shape (Dice coefficient closer to 1.0) has the potential to mitigate this discrepancy, especially for low SDR conditions. This is especially relevant in the cases where MRI-based skull regions were too thin compared to CT, as those regions will be less attenuating compared to CT-based modeling.

Despite the CT-derived masks predicting a marginally larger volume size than the MRI-derived masks, this difference was not associated with SDR variations. Furthermore, our analysis revealed that the greatest standard deviation in the error for maximum pressure predictions was observed in the left and right frontal cortex (F5, F7, F8), some locations in the parietal and occipital lobes. Similarly, the most substantial standard deviation in the error for volume size estimations was found at the F5, F7, Oz and Iz locations. Although the custom settings improved the estimations, these locations still exhibited significant

Figure 4. Measurements at the frequency of 500 kHz under default settings. (A) The mean and standard deviation of the maximum pressure error in % for each electroencephalogram (EEG) location. (B) The mean and standard deviation of the volume size error in % for each EEG location. (C) The mean and standard deviation of the focus location error in mm for each EEG location. The locations are sorted as a function of the standard deviation of the error metric. Triangles indicate the standard deviation of the error at each EEG location, while small circles represent the mean error at each EEG location. For better visualization and readability, extreme values are displayed as mean (SD) on the figure. (D) Color map representing the standard deviation of the error for each EEG location concerning maximum pressure, volume size, and focus location, providing a visual summary of the observed variability.

variability in the error for volume size estimations across different SDRs.

It is worth noting that simulations using MRI-derived skull masks can attain satisfactory precision across numerous EEG sites. Yet, significant errors at specific sites highlight the need for careful selection of the stimulation location when choosing between CT- and MRI-derived skull modeling approaches. The median of focus location error between CT- and MRI-derived skull masks can reach up to 2.67 mm across various frequencies and SDRs. While this dis-

crepancy might seem minor, it can become crucial for certain applications, especially when considering the dimensions of the target region.

It is important to recognize that significant errors may stem from various factors associated with the masks generated under MRI and CT conditions. Specifically, the MRI-derived masks may exhibit differences in both thickness and shape, which can influence the accuracy of the results. Additionally, the MRI-derived masks are modeled as simple three-layer structures—cortical (10%), trabecular (80%),

Figure 5. Measurements at the frequency of 500 kHz under custom settings. (A) The mean and standard deviation of the maximum pressure error for each electroencephalogram (EEG) location. (B) The mean and standard deviation of the volume size error for each EEG location. (C) The mean and standard deviation of the focus location error for each EEG location. The locations are sorted as a function of the standard deviation of the error metric. Triangles indicate the standard deviation of the error at each EEG location, while small circles represent the mean error at each EEG location. For better visualization and readability, extreme values are displayed as mean (SD) on the figure. (D) Color map representing the standard deviation of the error for each EEG location concerning maximum pressure, volume size, and focus location, providing a visual summary of the observed variability.

and cortical (10%)—and do not provide voxel-level information. This limitation contrasts with CT-derived masks, which offer a more precise representation of skull anatomy due to their ability to capture detailed structural information.

The underestimation of skull thickness in MRI-based masks can be attributed to several factors. Tissue contrast in MRI varies depending on the sequence used and the scanner itself. For example, in T1-weighted images, both compact bone and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) appear dark, making it challenging to accurately define the boundary between

these structures. While T2-weighted scans, where CSF appears bright, typically improve segmentation accuracy, differences in tissue boundaries between MRI and CT remain. Artifacts such as the fat shift in MRI, which displaces the spongy bone compartment, and the lower resolution of MRI compared to CT, which increases the partial volume effect that blurs tissue borders, further contribute to this discrepancy. These factors are particularly pronounced in thinner skull regions, such as the temporal lobes, leading to systematic misestimation of skull thickness in MRI-derived masks.

Table 2. The median of the error (95% confidence intervals), for each skull density ratio (SDR) and each analyzed variable.

Frequency	SDR	Condition	Max pressure error (%)	Volume size error (%)	Focus location error (mm)	
250 kHz	SDR 0p31	Default setting	25.64 (19.62, 34.07)	16.18 (8.38, 28.77)	2.04 (1.71, 2.7)	
		Custom setting	14.5 (8.09, 20.3)	8.75 (3.82, 32.08)	2.3 (1.76, 2.83)	
	SDR 0p42	Default setting	10.49 (7.6, 13.64)	12.92 (3.71, 29.14)	2.67 (2.42, 3.22)	
		Custom setting	8.24 (2.06, 12.67)	14.43 (-1.97, 27.85)	2.07 (1.59, 2.53)	
	SDR 0p55	Default setting	-7.22 (-12.54, -3.93)	13.46 (5.19, 23.49)	1.9 (1.42, 2.58)	
		Custom setting	-12.86 (-17.29, -4.27)	9.43 (6.07, 19.75)	1.56 (1.19, 2.44)	
	SDR 0p67	Default setting	14.56 (11.7, 22.16)	7.01 (-3.65, 13.85)	2.48 (1.85, 2.89)	
		Custom setting	14.04 (5.76, 22.19)	4.53 (-5.5, 11.43)	2.4 (1.82, 2.93)	
	SDR 0p79	Default setting	11.54 (5.38, 15.88)	6.51 (-1.58, 11.14)	2.49 (1.95, 2.9)	
		Custom setting	3.37 (-3.3, 10.15)	0.89 (-5.9, 14.73)	2.1 (1.29, 2.59)	
	500 kHz	SDR 0p31	Default setting	29.54 (18.57, 36.46)	-4.86 (-17.68, -1.07)	1.53 (1.38, 1.82)
			Custom setting	18.16 (12.88, 26.36)	-11.28 (-14.99, -3.31)	1.8 (1.5, 2.38)
SDR 0p42		Default setting	24.75 (16.98, 35.52)	-10.33 (-13.83, -4.2)	1.31 (1.09, 1.66)	
		Custom setting	13.79 (8.1, 17.69)	-7.33 (-11.74, -5.14)	1.09 (0.84, 1.4)	
SDR 0p55		Default setting	-3.06 (-6.94, -0.13)	-5.64 (-11.46, -1.56)	1.26 (1.03, 1.38)	
		Custom setting	-7.07 (-14.9, -4.02)	-0.82 (-9.05, 5.34)	1.13 (0.84, 1.38)	
SDR 0p67		Default setting	-2.88 (-8.86, -1.28)	-9.77 (-14.88, -6.15)	1.47 (1.07, 1.86)	
		Custom setting	-8.47 (-14.31, -1.97)	-5.99 (-13.47, -1.12)	1.38 (1.19, 1.71)	
SDR 0p79		Default setting	-12.33 (-16.32, -9.13)	-9.11 (-14.8, -2.97)	1.67 (1.28, 2.2)	
		Custom setting	-9.75 (-20.66, -5.99)	-14.29 (-18.29, -7.44)	1.5 (0.97, 2.01)	
750 kHz		SDR 0p31	Default setting	44.34 (21.48, 65.77)	-22.49 (-30.76, -15.19)	1.73 (1.12, 2.18)
			Custom setting	19.14 (8.77, 31.39)	-9.45 (-17.56, 1.97)	1.77 (1.46, 2.53)
	SDR 0p42	Default setting	11.61 (6.14, 15.56)	-8.7 (-16.39, -6.12)	1.62 (1.18, 1.9)	
		Custom setting	4.32 (-1.48, 11.72)	-9.02 (-12.11, -2.26)	1.48 (1.03, 1.97)	
	SDR 0p55	Default setting	-8.46 (-13.11, -2.67)	-9.06 (-15, -2.97)	1.13 (0.86, 1.62)	
		Custom setting	-15.06 (-20.80, -9.09)	-1.15 (-7.71, 5.95)	0.96 (0.79, 1.23)	
	SDR 0p67	Default setting	-25.52 (-27.86, -18.10)	-13.62 (-21.05, -7.53)	1.55 (1.16, 2.01)	
		Custom setting	-27.32 (-31.49, -19.77)	-10.06 (-18.34, -6.33)	1.59 (1.14, 1.99)	
	SDR 0p79	Default Setting	-27.81 (-34.00, -22.78)	-20.61 (-23.05, -16.70)	1.82 (1.17, 2.40)	
		Custom Setting	-33.1 (-38.15, -25.62)	-13.98 (-17.22, -9.08)	1.42 (1.04, 1.83)	

The plots provided in figures 4 and 5 (see appendix for the frequencies of 250 and 750 kHz) sort the locations as a function of the standard deviation of the error metrics. This arrangement helped to identify the locations that are less sensitive to the use of MRI-based processing, in the sense the predictions are closer to being constant across all SDR values.

Although ZTE, UTE, and PETRA for MR scanning may not be available at all scanner sites, these techniques are noteworthy alternatives to T1- and T2-weighted imaging for enhancing the accuracy of MRI-based ultrasound simulations. Adopting ZTE, UTE, or PETRA can be particularly effective for generating synthetic CT scans. This method aids in the construction of pseudo-CT scans [23, 28], presenting a promising approach to improve the precision of skull modeling.

5. Limitations

Our simulations were conducted with a cohort of five participants, encompassing a broad spectrum of

SDRs. However, one limitation of our study is the reliance on this small sample size, potentially limiting the generalizability of our findings across all SDRs. Other limitations of our study were the exclusion of some targets, necessitated by the defacement of the MRI and CT scans and the use of a single depth for targeting, which is representative only of cortical targets. For deeper targets, it would be expected that the differences between MRI- and CT-based processing could be more important, but further studies are required. Nevertheless, the scope of the present study can present an initial assessment as a function of the intended trajectory to be explored to reach a particular target.

6. Conclusions

MRI-based simulations already demonstrate reasonable accuracy at numerous EEG locations, and the tested custom settings helped to further improve the accuracy of ultrasound planning using MRI scans. However, significant errors at certain locations underscore the importance of careful site selection. This

highlights a critical insight: the choice between CT- and MRI-derived skull modeling needs to consider the to-be-expected error of MRI-based simulations specifically for the intended target brain region(s). Our study not only contributes valuable data on the feasibility and accuracy of using MRI-derived skull modeling but also calls for continued refinement in simulation methodologies to enhance treatment precision and safety.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available at the following URLs/DOIs:

- Imaging data: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7894431>.

- Source code and custom settings: https://github.com/ProteusMRIgHIFU/EnhanceTUS_Zadeh_JNE.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Authorship contribution statement

Ali K. Zadeh: Writing—review & editing, Writing—original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Modeling Execution, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Oula Puonti:** Methodology, Writing—review & editing, **Björn Sigurðsson:** Methodology, Segmentation Design, Writing—review & editing, **Axel Thielscher:** Methodology, Writing—review & editing, **Oury Monchi:** Writing—review & editing, **Samuel Pichardo:** Methodology, Modeling Design and Coding, Writing—review & editing.

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